

Misuse of prescribed medications in older adults: understanding a facet of the global health and healthcare crisis

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Abstract

The misuse of controlled medicines is a global healthcare crisis with widespread impact that poses challenges for older people, especially given the vulnerability of older people due to age-related health conditions and the complexity of polypharmacy. This study carried out for RAUN and UNODC focuses on prescription medication misuse among older adults, emphasizing person-centred approaches, medication safety in polypharmacy, and safe access to needed medications. Using a mixed-methods empirical strategy combining quantitative and qualitative data (including semi-structured expert interviews and in depth, open interviews with elderly individuals and their caretakers), aimed to understand the impact of the social environment on the misuse of controlled medicines in older people, identify best practices for healthcare providers and caregivers, and assess the pros and cons of digital solutions in preventing older people's misuse of medicines. Findings suggest that prescribing procedures should be improved through a thorough assessment of medical history, consideration of underlying medical conditions, potential interactions, and overall health status. It is crucial to develop educational campaigns for caregivers and older adults, as well as using AI technology to develop user-friendly solutions. In addition, challenging societal stereotypes, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration, and conducting regular medication reviews can help to achieve comprehensive medication management and promote the well-being of older adults. In turn, these findings served the authors to develop policy suggestions for addressing the issue of misuse of prescribed medications in the elderly population (+65), aligning with UNODC's goals.

Keywords: Misuse, Controlled Medicine, Prescription, Older People, Medication Safety,

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1. Introduction

The international medication control began with the 1912 Opium Convention and evolved through subsequent League of Nations conventions. The core framework consists of three major treaties: the 1961 Single Convention, the 1971 Psychotropics Convention, and the 1988 Trafficking Convention. The UN medication control conventions bind countries to ban non-medical or scientific use of controlled medicines.

The misuse of controlled medicine¹, a global healthcare crisis with health and societal repercussions, leads to diverse issues ranging from short-term accidents to long-term consequences like dependence and mental health disorders. Given their vulnerability due to age-related health conditions and the complexities of polypharmacy, focus is needed for the growing population of older adults (<65).

However, the elderly population confronts a paradox. On one side, stringent regulation, a response to substance abuse crises (like the opioid epidemic in the USA), may hinder older adults' access to certain medications. Conversely, the elderly itself may be susceptible to substance misuse, influenced by factors such as the number of prescribed medications, potential interactions between medications, and instances of over prescription or misprescription aimed at simplifying caregiving for older individuals.

This research aims to analyse prescribed medication misuse in the elderly. with a special focus on exploring (1) elderly person-centred approaches to medicine prescription, (2) medication safety, especially in polypharmacy and (3) secure access to the required medication (for each patient).

By using Europe as a study-area and Spain as a focus case, this research is constructed around the following three research questions: (1) How does the social environment, including formal and informal care providers, influence (exacerbate or mitigate) controlled medicine misuse among older adults? (2) What are the best practices for healthcare providers and caregivers to strike a balance between ensuring medication access and preventing misuse among the elderly? (3) What are the

¹ "Controlled medicines" encompass medications regulated by three major international medication treaties: The Single Convention on Narcotic Medications of 1961 (as amended by the 1972 Protocol), the Convention on Psychotropic Substances of 1971, and the United Nations Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Medications and Psychotropic Substances of 1988. When used as prescribed, these medications effectively treat various medical conditions. However, their non-medical use and misuse, including taking prescription medications without a valid prescription or using them improperly, are growing public health concerns. This definition is from the 2012 WHO Guidelines and RAUN questionnaire to Elizabeth Saenz (UNODC officer).

pros and cons of digital solutions in assisting the elderly to avoid the abuse of controlled medications?

To answer these research questions, we developed a mixed-methods empirical strategy that combined quantitative and qualitative data (see this report, “research design and strategy”). While we used already existing quantitative data, filtered to fit our research needs, we generated qualitative data by ourselves, focusing on (1) experts and (2) patients experiences surrounding prescribed medication (mis)use. For this we combined two surveying methods: semi-structured interviews and in depth, non-structured, conversational interviews or ethnographic interviews (see Wenster & Rice 2019). All interviewees were chosen according to purposive sampling methods (see Palinkas et al. 2015). To analyse the data obtained, we followed analysing protocols stemming from anthropology and ethnography, namely note taking and transcribing, categorising of the information of each interview by topic and information interpolation. In order to broaden our interpretative capacity, we not only undertook an informed, comprehensive analysis of the data in the light of the literature and existing knowledge on the subject but also compared the information with information from very different, contrasting social environments - such as China and Hungary².

China and Hungary emerge as two interesting cases to compare with the Spanish case. Firstly, Hungary appears as another country in the European region with demographic trends similar to those of Spain, and very similar medicalisation models when it comes to the elderly (see Figure 3). The proximity of both contexts facilitates comparison, and the investigative results and proposed measures to alleviate the misuse of medication in the elderly population in the Spanish case could potentially be applied to Hungary. Meanwhile, China, although it has a healthcare system very different from Spain's and Hungary's, exhibits demographic trends that demand placing the elderly person at the centre. Specifically, the one-child policy has generated a demographic profile where the elderly population is supported by a younger generation composed of only children, who must assume a heavy caregiving burden. This contrasts with the Spanish and Hungarian cases, where families tend to be larger, providing enormous comparative potential and aiding in the interpretation of different phenomena in both contexts. In conclusion, both cases enhance the robustness of the study and elevate it to a European regional and global scale, with the inclusion of the Chinese case.

The results found, together with the discussion of our finds, are available in this report.

2. State of the art

2.1. Misuse of Controlled Medications among Elderly

² The comparison with Hungary is interesting. Both countries have similar percentages of older people taking medication (see Figure 3). According to data from the China Social Security Association, by 2020 China's elderly population aged over 65 has reached 191 million, accounting for 13.5 per cent of the total population, and more than 180 million elderly people are suffering from chronic diseases, with one Chinese out of every four elderly people in the world. Due to the large elderly medication base, the experience of Chinese experts and patients is also very informative, and we found a lot of similarities from the interviews of experts and individuals regarding the prescribed medicine in the elderly between Hungary, Spain and China

The prevalence of medication prescriptions among older adults is notably high, surpassing rates of alcohol, over-the-counter medications, or illicit medications (Lofwall et al., 2005; Han et al., 2009; Qato et al., 2008; Gossop and Moos, 2008; Culberson & Ziska, 2008). Research indicates that prescribed medication misuse is more prevalent in the older population than other substances. Regarding the reason of the prescription, older people are the age-group most likely to be prescribed opiates for pain (Immonen et al., 2013), chronic pain, insomnia, and anxiety (Culberson & Ziska, 2008) that may be why the focus have been controlled medicine misuse related to pain and palliative care (especially cancer-related). On average, older adults in care settings take between one and five scheduled medications daily. In addition, they concurrently use nonprescription medications (José Joaquín Mira, 2019; Paula A Rochon, et al.2022). Paula A Rochon, et al.'s (2022) study concluded that polypharmacy, in which a patient uses multiple medications, is common in older adults and may lead to adverse events, medication-medication interactions, and physical and cognitive decline. It is estimated that about 7% of prescriptions contain errors, usually due to inappropriate prescribing or prescribing errors, affecting 58% of elderly patients. Medication administration errors account for 19.1% of the total opportunity for error, with about half of these errors occurring during intravenous administration (Laatikainen, 2022).

Regarding the reasons for the misuse, it appears linked to depressive symptoms (Holtfreter et al. 2015), among other causes. Regarding possible health outcomes, some studies contemplate the relation of mental health and prescription medication misuse, or at least mentioned it as a relevant issue to take in account when addressing the use (De Lema Larre, 2015; Rosen et al., 2008) and the need to understand how medication abuse interacts with age-related changes in the brain (Dowling et al., 2007). And the elderly are more vulnerable to the harm of psychoactive medication misuse due to increased physical and psychological illnesses (Xiong et al., 2019; Gong et al., 2018). Prolonged high-dose usage can worsen their conditions. Many older adults misuse prescription medications, often combined with alcohol, leading to adverse effects. Opioids have a stronger impact, sometimes inducing hallucinations, and sedative-hypnotic medications increase cognitive decline and toxicity risk (Xiao, 2012; Li, 2003). Users experience worsened health, sleep quality, and overall quality of life and well-being. Psychoactive medication use can lead to physical and psychological dependence, and combining them with other medications increases the risk of health complications (see Boddiger, 2008; Thompsell et al., 1958). Additionally, in nursing homes, there is a problem with overmedication of the elderly, where some receive inappropriate medications or high doses, it's crucial to better inform healthcare providers about the risks and contraindications associated with prescription medication use in the elderly (UNODC, 2011a).

2.2. The Accessibility Problem of Controlled Medicine among Elderly

The misuse of controlled medicines also can cause social stigma and medical supply issues.³ For instance, when certain substances are misused, it can result in overly restrictive regulations, ultimately limiting legitimate patients from accessing the medications they could benefit from.⁴ The

³ Dr. Mercy W. Karanja from the Ministry of Health, Kenya. Talk given at the Technical Consultation Meeting on Availability of and Access to Controlled Medicines in Vienna, September 28, 2023.

⁴ Ibidem.

United Nations (UN) has extensively researched and documented the global issue of limited access to opioid-based medications, particularly pain relievers. This concern is underscored by various UN publications, including discussion papers (UNODC, 2011a; b), a technical guidance document (UNODC, 2018), and a resolution (UNODC, 2010). The information available on the UNODC website, specifically under "Access to Controlled Medications for Medical Purposes (GLOK67)," further amplifies the critical nature of this issue.

The key focal point of this research is the stark contrast between the abundant supply of opioid-based medications and the inadequate access to these essential medications in many regions. The UN emphasises the necessity of striking a delicate balance between ensuring accessibility for legitimate medical purposes and preventing the misuse and abuse of controlled substances. This duality of the problem positions it as both a health and healthcare issue, with a particular vulnerability observed among the elderly population.

Scientific evidence underscores the vital role of controlled medicines, including opioids, in achieving optimal health outcomes, especially in managing pain. However, a pervasive global inequity exists due to the under-treatment of pain resulting from the unavailability of these medicines (INCB, 2020; Knaul et al., 2018; Nchako et al., 2018). The urgency of addressing this disparity cannot be overstated, as the under-treatment of pain impacts people in over 150 countries, encompassing approximately 80% of the global population. It is imperative to take prompt and comprehensive action to rectify this situation and ensure that individuals worldwide, regardless of geographic location, have access to the pain relief they require. This multifaceted challenge demands a concerted effort to bridge the gap between the ample supply of controlled medicines and their insufficient accessibility, particularly for vulnerable demographics such as the elderly.

2.3. The Digital Medication Management Systems among Elderly

Turjamaa, Riitta, et al. (2022) highlight the importance of safe medication management in care services and the potential benefits of digital solutions such as robotics. Digital solutions enable older people to live longer in their own homes and reduce the number of daily visits by home care professionals and hospitalisation rates. They are therefore considered a suitable solution for older people living in remote areas with limited access to home care professionals (Nakrem et al., 2018; Schelisch & Walter, 2021).

Digital solutions have been developed for implementing the medication process in the homes of older people, and digital solutions for smart medication management include apps as well as sensors and robots to remind older people to take the right medication at the right time (Turjamaa, Riitta, et al., 2022). Like medication management robotic system (MMR) (Iqbal, Sarfraz, et al., 2021), Robot Pria, and A prototypical software application based on the NAO-robot platform (Schweitzer, M. and Hoerbst, A., 2016) et al. Many studies by scholars Turjamaa, Riitta, et al. (2022); Glomsås et al. (2020); and Kleiven, et al. (2020) have argued that in the implementation of medication administration robots, there is a need for timely education and training prior to the use of the robots, as well as timely technical support. According to Schelisch and Walter (2021), sustainable digital networks depend on effective participant interaction and beneficial synergies, highlighting the social and technical complexities at play. Before launching a digital project, understanding site-specific issues and potential non-digital resolutions is crucial.

Acceptance and attitudes to AI among carers and older people is also an issue. Some research indicates that home care professionals may hold scepticism and biases towards digital solutions due to the increased workload associated with the adoption of new technologies. Additionally, they express uncertainty about their own capabilities in utilising digital solutions (Andersson et al., 2017; Persson et al., 2021). Understandably, a lack of e-health literacy and insufficient training can lead to frustration among home care professionals (Frennert, 2019). Several studies suggest that home care professionals play a significant role in encouraging the use of these robots in eldercare at home (Johansson-Pajala & Gustafsson, 2020; Persson et al., 2021). Furthermore, home care professionals emphasise the need to ensure sufficient cognitive and physical abilities in elderly clients before implementing robot-assisted medication management (Turjamaa, Riitta, et al., 2022).

3. Theoretical background

The theoretical foundation of the research is focused on “person-centred care”, encapsulating the personalization of care by emphasising holistic, flexible, creative, and unique solutions (Edvardsson, 2015). Originating from nursing and disciplines caring for age-related conditions, this perspective addresses the challenges posed by an ageing population, presenting an ideal solution for effective healthcare services (Ekman et al., 2013). While person-centred care advocates for a non-reductionist approach, there's uncertainty about specific elements promoting it in various contexts and the necessary systems for implementation (Edvardsson, 2015). Research in this area prioritises collecting and utilising life stories, especially in caring for older individuals and those with dementia.

In the digital era, a significant solution in the Global North is "person-centred technology-enabled care," leveraging technology to enhance patient involvement in health without face-to-face visits (Dyb et al., 2021). However, the suitability of technological solutions for older adults, particularly in the context of (mis)use of controlled medicines, remains uncertain. Recent studies have explored the intersection between person-centred technological care and the geriatric population, but the extent to which these solutions enhance or hinder person-centred care remains unclear (Bally et al., 2022; Hung, 2020).

To theorise technology acceptance in this context, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is considered valuable. TAM, widely used in diverse research studies, aims to predict technology adoption and identify potential design challenges. In health technologies, the "Healthcare Technology Acceptance Model (H-TAM)" specifically addresses technology acceptance in healthcare (Mun et al., 2006; Chau & Hu, 2002; Harris & Rogers, 2023), which supports the suitability of TAM application in health-related research.

4. Research Design and Strategy

This research focuses on understanding factors influencing controlled medicine misuse and medication safety among older Europeans, with a focus on Spain. Despite our regional focus driven by linguistic and geographical limitations, Europe as a region, with a focus on Spain, provides a

compelling case study with shared ageing trends (*Figure 1*)⁵, cultural attitudes, readily available official statistics and optimal accessibility to implement qualitative methods.

To answer our research questions, we designed a strategy that takes into accounts not only the interest of our research, but the foundational knowledge gaps that exist in the literature, mainly: the lack of standardisation when referring to the meaning of “older adults”, “prescribed medications”, “misuse” etc., and the overrepresentation of the United States of America, as most of the Academic literature was concerned with this context. In this light, we have decided to implement an empirical approach based on mixed-methods, emphasising qualitative research for firsthand data collection and quantitative analysis of existing data for survey design and result interpretation. More precisely, our research strategy included:

4.1. Quantitative Strategy

First quantitative exploration of medication prescription to older adults (type of medicine, gender of the adult) in Spain in order to know better the nature of the general prescription situation in Spain. This helped both narrow the knowledge gap, as most of what we knew regarding medication prescription to older adults was focused on the USA. In turn, this helped to design our qualitative exploration more mindfully. This made our research more robust, as it implemented the comparative capacity of our results.

4.1.1. Origin of the Data

For the exploratory analysis of prescribed medicines consumption in Europe, the research relies on The European Health Interview Survey (EHIS), collected and made available by the statistical office of the European Union (EUROSTAT)⁶ and the Spanish *Instituto Nacional de Estadística* (INE).

Regarding the data available at EUROSTAT, the European Health Interview Survey was designed to measure, in a standardised manner, various aspects related to the utilisation of health care services by the European Union (EU), including the use of prescribed medications. The survey was carried out by each of the Member States. The survey targets individuals aged 15 and above residing in private households within the member states’ territories. It underwent development between 2003 and 2006 and was conducted in waves from 2008 to 2020⁷. More in detail, the dataset used in this research is allocated within the “Health care” topic, which covers the use of different types of medicines (prescribed and non-prescribed) and allows for a comparative perspective of each Member State of the EU. This information was fundamental to understand our case of study (Spain) from a comparative perspective and understand where it stands within its immediately broader regional area.

⁵ To see this figure, go to Annexe 1.

⁶ Metadata in Euro SDMX Metadata Structure (ESMS). Compiling agency: Eurostat, the statistical office of the European Union. Consulted November 13, 2023. [Accessed 14/03/2024] https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/hlth_det_esms.htm

⁷ For more information on the design and implementation of the questionnaires go to: European health interview survey - methodology. (Latest update July 2021). EUROSTAT Statistic explained. Consulted November 13, 2023. [Accessed 14/03/2024] https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=European_health_interview_survey_-_methodology

Regarding the data available at INE, it contained the raw data collected for the European Health Survey in the Spanish case, which allows for an in-depth exploration of this case. The datasets employed are allocated within the Health Care category and “Medicine Consumption”. The survey targeted individuals aged 15 years and older residing in family dwellings across the entire national territory (22,000 dwellings strategically distributed across 2,500 census sections) and was carried out in the year 2020. The sampling method employed was stratified tri-stage sampling, ensuring its representativeness. Data collection was carried out through a meticulous process involving computer-assisted personal and telephone interviews.⁸

4.1.2. Datasets description

In the case of EUROSTAT, we explored a pre-existing dataset named “Self-reported use of prescribed medicines by sex, age and country of citizenship” (code hlth_ehis_md1c, data coverage: 2014 — 2019, last update: 11-11-2022, number of values: 9 576). This allowed us to filter the data by age and country of citizenship to generate the desired result (see results) section.

In the case of INE, we worked with pre-existing datasets to obtain new ones that allowed us to obtain the information desired (see results section). All of the data used refer to consumption of prescribed medicines over 2 weeks, by gender and age. This allowed us to explore the consumption of prescribed medicines within the elderly, by type of medicine and gender, and also to compare prescribed medication consumption among different age groups in the country. The datasets used were: (1) Consumption of medicines in the last 2 weeks whether prescribed or not by sex and age group. Population aged 15 and over⁹; and (2) Type of medicine used in the last 2 weeks, by sex and age group. Population aged 15 years and over using each type of medicine in the last 2 weeks¹⁰.

4.2. Qualitative Strategy

As mentioned above, an ideal analytical strategy for understanding the needs of person-centred care - which advocates for a non-reductionist, non-standardised, non-detached and non-task-based approach to care - is the analysis of individual cases through the immersive exploration of older people’s experiences of (mis)use of medicines and their environment (Edvardsson 2015). Similarly, the academic literature underlines the importance of collecting information and experience from subject matter experts, healthcare providers and other stakeholders with extensive experience of the phenomenon of (mis)use of medicines. This is especially true when it comes to assessing the empowerment (harm or benefit) of digital and technological solutions and finding creative, effective and respectful ways to implement them (Dyb & Kvam, 2021).

⁸ INE - Instituto Nacional de Estadística. (s. f.). INEbase / Sociedad / Salud / Encuesta europea de Salud en España / Metodología. INE. [Accessed 14/03/2024]

https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/es/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176784&menu=metodologiaa&idp=1254735573175

⁹ [Accessed 14/03/2024]

<https://www.ine.es/jaxi/Datos.htm?path=/t15/p420/a2019/p02/l0/&file=07001.px#!tabs-grafico>

¹⁰ [Accessed 14/03/2024]

<https://www.ine.es/jaxi/Tabla.htm?path=/t15/p420/a2019/p02/l0/&file=07011.px&L=0>

4.2.1. Data Collection

This research focus encompasses semi-structured interviews with two key groups: health experts and providers (6 individuals), and elderly people and their social environments (4 cases), namely informal carers (usually family members).

Health experts:

For the interview with the health experts, we designed a template that combined the description of the study and the conditions of the interview (always in accordance with research ethics protocols) and the questions of the questionnaire, which was designed to guide the interview but also to be flexible. The questions were designed to encourage the experts to reflect on different aspects of prescription medication misuse in the over-65 populations, adapting the template to each expert's area of expertise. As mentioned above, the experts were selected using the 'purposive' sampling method, i.e. we contacted experts with ideal profiles to answer our research questions. The profiles of each expert were interesting on their own and in combination with each other, as they complemented each other to gain a better understanding of the issue. Here is a description of the background of each expert, whose names will be anonymised:

Expert 1: Doctor, specialising in general practice. Former doctor in deprived urban setting in Spain. Currently working as an expert in the regional government health administration of the *Comunidad de Madrid*.

Expert2: Doctor, specialising in surgery, general practice and family and community medicine in the Basque Country and Spain. Expert on how ageing is tackled in primary care with abundant scientific publications on the issue.

Expert3: Professor of labour law and social security at the university, a member of the European Committee of Social Rights (ECSR) of the Council of Europe. specialised in labour law and social security law, including occupational health and safety (OHS) and medical care.

Expert4: Doctor specialising in epidemiology, haematology and general practice. Abundant experience as a GP treating the elderly and reflecting on elderly care.

Expert5: Doctor and Anthropologist with wide expertise on ageism, and social stigma more generally. Experience working at WHO with a global understanding of the issue.

Expert6: MD, focusing on quality patient care, patient care and direct patient care, with extensive practical experience in hospitals.

Regarding the questionnaires themselves (Appendix A), they were designed in accordance with our research questions, targeting experiences of prescribed medications (mis)use, medication intake experiences (systems implemented, limitations etc.), and digital solutions (both in use and missing). Interviews with experts were conducted in English and Spanish (versions of the questionnaires in both languages were available), adapting the language of the interviews to the preferences of the experts.

Regarding data collection and processing: as mentioned above, during the interviews, which lasted between 30 minutes and 1.5 hours, notes were taken of the experts' statements and the parts that the researchers considered most important were transcribed verbatim. The interviews were mostly

conducted by telephone, although two interviews were conducted in person and one in writing, as the expert decided to give his or her opinion on the issues raised in writing. The information collected will be kept by the researchers, but will not be presented verbatim or in full. The experiences of each expert were grouped into different overarching themes in order to bring them together and highlight commonalities and differences between them, and put the information provided into conversation with each other (see Results section).

The found overarching themes were: (1) misuse definition (is misuse misprescription? Or literally misuse?); (2) Recommendations to prevent misuse; (3) risks of medication (mis)use by the elderly; and (4) Social and environmental phenomena.

Elderly people and their social environments¹¹:

Interviews with people over 65 and their environment (family and informal carers) were conducted as open discussions about their lifestyle, health status, medication use, organisation of daily life, etc. Most of them were conducted through 1:1 interview with the persons responsible for medication management (informal carers). On one occasion, a face-to-face interview was conducted with several members of the household present. The rest were conducted over several visits and telephone calls, which allowed us to explore some interesting aspects in depth as new information was gathered.

The cases (elderly people and their social environments) were chosen following purposive sampling, based on the adequacy of the cases to our previous findings derived from literature review, our mentor's experience and results from quantitative exploration of prescribed medicine consumption. The information was collected through note taking during and after the conversations, with the explicit and informed consent of the participants. The results were analysed in order to detect common narratives and key elements and situations of controlled medicines misuse, its prevention, or its remedy.

The life experiences collected cover different socio-economic, family and health profiles (from older adults in very good health to people with severe morbidity or multimorbidity). One of the informal caregivers works in a nursing home¹², which allowed us to get some impressions of this environment, although the interviews explore cases where older people live in their private or family homes. Not all of the people we selected were fully interviewed due to different limitations. A list of the final study cases used in this research and their main characteristics is given below:

Case1: 66-year-old woman caring for her 68-year-old husband and 100-year-old mother-in-law. Rural setting. Spain. Various health conditions. Various medicine types.

¹¹ Interviews are still ongoing – the information presented here might change slightly in the definite version of this report.

¹² Although nursing homes and daycare centres are high-risk settings for inappropriate use of prescribed medication, research limitations prevented us from accessing institutions of this type, due to the greater restriction of conducting ethnographic research in institutions. A future study of this style, based on the current findings, remains open as an interesting line of future research, of great relevance and great potential.

Case2: An elderly woman (87) in a situation of multimorbidity (cognitive impairment included). Lived alone, disordered rhythm of eating and sleeping. Moved with her daughter and grandkids. Urban Spain.

Case3: 57-year-old son taking care of his 88-year-old mother. Heart problem (they got a heart attack 2 years ago), varicose veins problem, diabetes and several small diseases. Urban setting, Szeged, Hungary.

Case4: 32-year-old grandson taking care of his 90-year-old grandfather Urban setting. Qingzhou, China.

5. Results

5.1. Quantitative

5.1.1. European region overview – focus EU

According to the preliminary exploration published by EUROSTAT in relation to the intake of prescribed medication in Europe, the following state for the region was detected¹³. In the European Union (EU), the use of prescription medicines varies considerably between Member States, with use rates above 55% in Portugal, Finland, Belgium and Croatia, and below 40% in Italy and Romania. In Spain, men's use of prescription medicines is higher than the EU average (52.3 %), and women's use (45.7 %) is higher than in 21 countries. In general, prescription medication use is lowest among people aged 15-24 and there is an age-related increase in use, peaking among those aged 75 and over. Notably, Spain exceeds EU levels of prescription medication use in all age groups. In 2019, a comprehensive analysis of men and women across the EU shows consistently higher prescription medication use among women in all age groups. Gender differences are more pronounced in younger and middle-aged groups, influenced by factors such as the use of contraceptive pills and hormone treatments for menopause. In older age groups, the gap narrows, with the smallest difference at 1.1 percentage points for those aged 75 and over. In Spain, the gender gap in the use of prescription medicines in the over-75 age group is 3.4 percentage points, higher than in the EU, and the use rate exceeds that of 25 countries for men and 18 countries for women. In the 65-74 age group, the gender gap is slightly smaller in Spain at 2.5 percentage points (compared with 3.3 percentage points in the EU).¹⁴

This information is consistent with our detailed and in-depth examination of data on prescribed medication use among older adults in Spain, where between 88.6 and 92.1 percent of the older population (both men and women) reported using prescribed medication. Similar percentages are reported from countries such as Greece, Hungary, Belgium, Portugal and the Czech Republic. In comparison, lower percentages are reported in countries such as Romania, Italy, Turkey, Latvia

¹³ *Medicine use statistics.* (s/f). Europa.Eu. [Accessed 14/03/2024] https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Medicine_use_statistics

¹⁴ *Medicine use statistics* (n.d.). [Accessed 14/03/2024] https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Medicine_use_statistics#Prescribed_medicines

and Estonia, where only 61.1 to 79.1 percent of the older population reported using prescribed medicines (see Figure 3¹⁵).

5.1.2. Use of prescribed medicines in Spain

Focusing on the Spanish population in particular, the data show that the over-65s are the group with the highest consumption of prescribed medicines, accounting for 38% of the total number of medicines prescribed (Figure 4). Within the over-65 population, the group with the highest number of prescriptions is the 65-74 age group, with a drastic reduction in use among the over-85s. It is in this group (over 85) that the largest difference in prescriptions between women and men is recorded, with women consuming almost twice as much (Figure 5).

Looking at the type of medicine most commonly prescribed, blood pressure medicines, painkillers and cholesterol medicines top the list. Key medicines such as antidepressants, tranquillisers, relaxants and sleeping pills rank eleventh and sixth respectively (Figure 5). However, it is interesting to note that, when filtered by gender, antidepressants, tranquillisers, relaxants and sleeping pills are most commonly prescribed to women (70.0 per cent and 73.1 per cent respectively). Painkillers are also prescribed to women at 68.1 percent, while the most commonly prescribed medicines in general (diabetes, heart, cholesterol...) register percentages of around 50 percent for each gender group (Figure 6).

5.2. Qualitative

5.2.1. Interviews with health experts

The results will be presented following the thread of the overarching themes detected after processing the inputs provided by the experts, namely: (1) misuse definition (is misuse misprescription? Or literally misuse?); (2) Recommendations to prevent misuse; (3) risks of medication (mis)use by the elderly; and (4) Social and environmental phenomena.

5.2.1.1. When does the misuse of prescribed medicines happen?

All experts agreed that the misuse of prescribed medication in the over-65 population occurs at different levels. Firstly, at the time of prescription, where physicians may prescribe too much, too little, or based on time or financial constraints, system overload, biases, or prejudices that may lead to inappropriate medication prescription (refer to 'section 5.2.1.3' on How social environment and life situations affect the misuse). Experts have noted a common issue among the older population: a backlog of medication resulting from indiscriminate prescribing and the accumulation of old and new prescriptions. This is closely linked to doctors failing to review existing prescriptions when prescribing new medication. This phenomenon is worsened during transitions of care, such as when a patient moves between different specialties within the same hospital, different health professionals, different health centres, or even different geographical regions. Conflicting medications may be prescribed by different doctors, or double prescriptions for the same medication may be issued (as reported in individual interviews).

¹⁵ To find the graphs, go to Annexe 1

On the other hand, misuse can occur during the actual use of the medicine by the patient. Misunderstandings about how the medication should be taken, its effects, and its purpose can arise due to lack of time during the doctor's appointment, particularly in cases of polypharmacy. There may be a discrepancy between what the doctor conveys and what the patient comprehends. This issue appears to be more common in lower socio-economic groups and in older adults with limited cognitive abilities and a smaller support system. Similarly, older individuals residing in nursing homes or day centres, where care is institutionalised, centralised and standardised, may be at greater risk of not adhering to prescribed treatments and medications, resulting in both over-medication and under-medication.

A third factor related to the distribution of medicines is the packaging and distribution format. For instance, medicines may be sold in boxes with a higher number of pills than the patient requires, resulting in medication waste and increasing the risk of the elderly or others consuming expired medicines with fatal health effects. However, packaging may result in the purchase of insufficient medication, causing the individual to run out of necessary medication before completing the treatment course.

5.2.1.2. Risks of prescribed medicines misuse

In the Spanish healthcare landscape, the nuanced risks associated with medication use underscore multifaceted concerns. Chronic use of antacids and anxiolytics, like Lexatin, raises worries due to potential dependency and intricate interactions with mental health dynamics. Administering psychotropic medications for mental health encounters hindrances from prevailing social stigmas. Analgesics, such as Paracetamol, Aspirin, and Ibuprofen, emblematic of the "quick fix" paradigm, carry distinct risks, including a propensity for bleeding and ulcers in the Spanish population, perhaps linked to hepatic metabolization concerns with Ibuprofen. Other analgesics, like Tramadol and Enantyum, meant for peripheral pain, require vigilant oversight within Spain's stringent opiate prescription protocols to forestall addiction. Advocating lifestyle changes over diuretics for blood pressure, along with dietary interventions and exercise, emerges as a potential avenue for mitigating risks associated with blood pressure medications. Addressing cholesterol concerns mandates emphasis on lifestyle modifications, especially considering the health predisposition, particularly among adult women undergoing menopausal transitions. Equally pivotal is scrutinising the normalised consumption of Lorazepam for sleep, unravelling proclivities toward addiction and potential renal and hepatic pathologies, necessitating an imperative exploration of underlying psychological and environmental triggers.

The risks associated with medication misuse in the elderly are multifaceted and impactful on their overall health. Some of the health problems that misusing prescribed medications can carry are as follows: inappropriate medication use may lead to increased vulnerability to falls due to side effects like dizziness. Cognitive decline is a potential consequence, impacting memory and mental function. Malnutrition may arise from medication side effects or interactions affecting appetite and nutrient absorption. Inappropriate medications can cause adverse effects, and polypharmacy-related complications, including medication conflicts, overdose, and increased susceptibility to side effects, are prevalent. These risks underscore the importance of vigilant medication management to prevent complications that can significantly impact the well-being of the elderly.

5.2.1.3. How do social environments and life situations affect the misuse?

The socio-cultural fabric of Spain, characterised by intergenerational cohabitation, inherently fosters a conducive environment for eldercare. However, an unintended consequence emerges in the form of medication accumulation within households, as "the box of medicines". While emblematic of familial support structures, this phenomenon necessitates nuanced attention to prevent instances of inadvertent misuse or overuse, as it can result in medication leaks towards other older adults and younger populations, or the risk of consuming medicines that went off.

Other experts have noted that firmly established collective beliefs in Spanish society, as well as in general, associate old age with illness. This can lead to risky behaviour in the elderly population, such as inappropriate or excessive prescribing based solely on age, even when the illness does not require it. This is particularly common in cases of multimorbidity and polypharmacy. This refers to the unfair treatment of patients based on their age rather than their health status. In addition, some experts agreed on the fact that there is limited awareness of the issue among healthcare professionals, patients, their relatives and the general public. One expert further highlighted the fact that among non-health professionals, the harmful effect of polypharmacy is rarely known. Another expert emphasises that even in professional education, still a lack of comprehensive patient education and physician training regarding medication use, while medical education covers drug interactions and prescribing guidelines, it often falls short in teaching how medications affect patients daily and how to tailor treatment plans to individual histories. And one expert, though, pointed to the fact that, in some cases, a lack of trust in the doctor's instructions might lead some patients to take smaller doses or not take at all prescribed medications.

Two experts have delineated the differentials in the healthcare provisions for elderly populations across urban and rural landscapes. Urban locales typically exhibit superior medical infrastructure characterised by heightened availability and quality of resources, facilities, and screening modalities. Moreover, healthcare practitioners in urban settings are frequently exposed to a more diverse caseload, fostering a milieu conducive to the continuous refinement of medical standards to enhance prescription efficacy and rationale. This environment often engenders the provision of comprehensive patient guidance. Conversely, rural environs often grapple with deficiencies in both healthcare personnel and equipment, thereby impeding effective medication oversight for older cohorts. The paucity of access to healthcare professionals and diagnostic apparatus exacerbates challenges about the monitoring and regulation of prescription medication utilisation among this demographic.

All experts agree that there is a pathologization of old age, leading to unnecessary medication. This is closely related to the concept of a 'quick fix' and individual expectations of well-being, with a low tolerance for age-related changes such as sleep patterns. Experts generally recommend comprehensive education on ageing and health, prioritising non-pharmacological treatments, particularly for mental health problems or other conditions that could be improved by adopting lifestyle changes. The unequal treatment and prescription of medicines to older adults is worsened when ageism intersects with sexism. For instance, in cases of depression, women are often over-diagnosed and over-prescribed, while men are frequently overlooked and under-prescribed for mental health issues.

Experts generally agree that bias affects not only the provision of health support to the geriatric population but also the extent of the problem. Clinical trials tend to focus on younger people, which means that many protocols for identifying processes related to pain and fatigue in the adult population are not well diagnosed or treated. This is often compounded by a lack of knowledge about the medication being taken, which can mean that surveys based on self-declared consumption of medicines do not fully reflect reality. Therefore, in order to measure, for example, the real transferability of the information given by doctors when prescribing, one expert stressed the need for surveyors to have health or pharmaceutical training and to be able to recognise the specific medicine that a person might be taking by the physical characteristics of the medicine itself, the colours of the packaging, etc., as well as the patient's symptoms¹⁶.

5.2.1.4. How to prevent the misuse of prescribed medicines?

With regard to possible solutions to prevent the inappropriate use of prescribed medication by the elderly population, the experts' recommendations were articulated around three axes: (1) how to improve the medical prescription system to avoid situations of excessive, inappropriate, or even conflicting prescriptions among various health professionals; (2) how to ensure that the guidelines given by the doctor (once they are appropriate and adjusted to each case) are followed by the patient; (3) how to change certain collective attitudes regarding the intake of prescribed medication. A fourth point would be (4) the implementation of digital and artificial intelligence-based solutions. This point will be explored independently, contrasting the opinions of different experts.

Firstly, the experts generally agreed on the need for an individualised approach to each case, taking into account first and foremost the needs of each patient, their state of health, but also their lifestyle, their living conditions (whether they have support networks etc.). At the same time, the experts agreed on the need to strengthen interdepartmental collaboration at all levels (between different health professionals, different specialities within hospitals and between different hospitals, even at the macro level, between different UN agencies that can respond to a problem that touches on medication use, health, gender, etc.).

The experts also insisted on the need to reinforce health education, some focusing on the training of health professionals themselves on how to correctly manage prescriptions in cases of multimorbidity, geriatrics, how to set therapeutic targets appropriate to the functional and life situation of the patients, and at the non-health professional level, by running health literacy campaigns not only aimed at older people but also at the younger generations, with the intention of changing attitudes and raising awareness on the issue (health literacy promotion); and at the non-health professional level, by carrying out health literacy campaigns not only aimed at the elderly but also at the younger generations, with the intention of changing attitudes and raising awareness on the subject (promotion of healthy habits, healthy ageing, basic health literacy, etc.).

¹⁶ As part of the interview, and following on from this theme, the researcher asked about narrative medicine approaches and the importance of narrative medicine and interviewer training (knowledge of types of medicine, colour etc. importance of physical attributes of medicine). Materiality and physicality of the medicines appeared then as an interesting option to control the misuse of prescribed medicines, and not only to enhance their commodifiability or marketability.

The need for the implementation of clear, effective and standardised protocols aimed at, on the one hand, generating and implementing clinical practice guidelines that address appropriate prescribing in multimorbidity scenarios in the elderly, but also monitoring protocols - one expert suggested nursing - to ensure follow-up on medication intake after prescription was also emphasised. One example provided was the implementation of a telephone follow-up system that would allow to know if the elderly person is taking the medication properly on the third and fifth day of treatment. Another suggestion that the two experts agreed on was to give prescription instructions in written form, and not only orally. For example, through a written description of how to take the medication (times etc.) or through standardised templates with ideally universal symbology (e.g. spoon for mealtime, moon for bedtime) that would allow older people to recognise the time of taking the medication almost automatically. Simultaneously, fostering a culture of regular check-ups and medication adjustments among the elderly can be beneficial.

Just as the experts agreed that an overloaded health system was responsible for an overburdening of health professionals, with its resulting pernicious effects (especially affecting the rural areas), most experts highlighted the importance of Primary Care in tackling the issue, as Primary Care professionals are able of a global assessment of the morbidity pattern of each subject, together with their socio-cultural environment, life and work conditions etc. and could be key agents in setting realistic, therapeutic and vital goals with the elderly, in order to de-prescribe appropriately.

Regarding the implementation of digital solutions, experts generally agree that, although they can have great advantages, they are tools to be handled with caution. For example, most of the experts pointed out the great benefits that a digital solution, even a tool linked to artificial intelligence, would work and work excellently as decision support elements for prescribing, training in multimorbidity management, citizen education etc. Even to monitor or automatise the medication intake at a user-level scale (apps that help patients and families to better manage their own treatments appeared as very useful). Remote monitoring tools also emerged as interesting solutions during the expert interviews. However, two experts mentioned important details when talking about the implementation of digital solutions: one of them is the potential cost associated not only with the globalised implementation of digital tools, which in most cases cannot replace human work (e.g. one expert mentioned the need for an efficient care network coupled with the implementation of remote falls detection systems). With regard to AI, one expert mentioned the importance of taking into account that AI is based on human models that currently produce ageist and sexist biases in the diagnosis and prescription of medication to older adults. The reproduction of such biases by artificial intelligence could give a tinge of objectivity to something that is biased.

Finally, experts agreed on the need to de-prescribe and encourage the older population towards healthier lifestyles, as well as to combat the social stigma associated with some conditions, especially in relation to mental health. In addition to this, it was generally emphasised that medication adjustment should also take place at the level of pharmacists, who should adapt packaging and sales to the needs of the prescribed treatment (both to avoid purchasing too much medication and to avoid purchasing too little medication). In this respect, one of the experts mentioned an alternative: a method that we can think of now is "smart pills" based on artificial intelligence technology, which can remind the elderly to take medication wisely, but it also requires a lot of initial capital investment. In addition, some experts believed that the current smart pills do not show superiority

over regular pillboxes, were more expensive, and follow-up maintenance (especially for older people) was problematic, an opinion that mirrors the caregivers' opinion. However, some expert showed a positive attitude towards more developed and integrated surveillance and AI technologies¹⁷. Another approach that was mentioned and that is already being practised in Japan, is the splitting of medicines, where the medicines are in separate packages according to the doctor's prescription instead of in a whole box, which may be able to reduce the overuse of medicines to a certain extent.

5.2.2. Interviews with elderly people and their environment

The life experiences studied represent diverse but representative profiles of the situations in which different older people find themselves. In all cases, the older people lived in their own homes or in the homes of their relatives, rather than in medical institutions such as nursing homes or day centres. However, their daily routines and living conditions varied between rural and urban areas, with two in Spain, one in Hungary and one in China.

The health status of the older people is also different, which makes it possible to compare different situations, such as the self-management of prescribed medication by older people living alone, the management of medication in cases of multimorbidity and polypharmacy by family members, and the management of prescribed medication in situations of reduced cognitive capacity of the older person.

Regarding the presentation of the information obtained from the interviews with older adults and their relatives or informal caregivers, it will be done in a narrative format, describing each case individually. The similarities and differences between the four cases, which will be discussed and elaborated upon in the next section.

Case1: Case 1 corresponds to a household unit made up of a family of three people over 65 (husband, wife and her mother-in-law), one of whom is over 100, the other around 80. The third member is both an older adult and the main informal carer. They live in a rural setting (Spain) and report having a very good health, and lifestyle: all three are active and have healthy social relationships, relying on their neighbours to share daily life events, concerns, health conditions... during daily walks. The medications they take are few and only the oldest has stable prescriptions (for blood pressure and bladder control). They did not elaborate on the precise medicines (i.e. did not give the names), but commented on physical qualities of them. The medicines are taken together in the morning with breakfast, which is served in the dining room. The 65-year-old woman prepares the breakfast and the pills. Occasionally, everyone takes medication prescribed for specific conditions such as constipation (usually flumil and/or paracetamol). Occasionally, if the problem is not too serious - a mild sore throat or stomach ache - they will take natural remedies based on

¹⁷ Reflection on different types of AI technologies, in the nursing field, can be broadly divided into three categories, monitoring technology, assistive technology and companion robots. AI technology for medication management can be divided into two aspects from the perspective of both patients and doctors, namely, to help doctors prescribe medication and to help patients manage medication. In terms of medication management, the most widely used products in practice are "smart pillboxes" or "smart dispensers" with reminder functions to help patients make decisions about whether to take their medications or not. These products vary from simple time monitoring to remote monitoring with apps.

honey and herbs such as chamomile. For pain, they sometimes take paracetamol, which they keep in a medicine chest in the kitchen – together with the other medicines. They never use natural remedies on the 100-year-old woman because they are afraid that her health will deteriorate quickly. In this case, they go to the doctor at the first sign of ailment, especially in winter. The doctor is not always available, only four days a week. But the pharmacy is always open.

Case2: The second case is of an 87-year-old woman whose cognitive abilities have deteriorated dramatically over the past year. She had lived alone – always in Spain, urban setting. Her son and daughter used to visit her every day, bringing her food which she only had to heat up. They also prepared the medication she had to take every day at lunchtime. The lady is in a situation of multimorbidity, so she takes several medications, which vary greatly depending on which doctor prescribes them (the general practitioner tends to prescribe a lot, while the geriatrician tends to reduce prescriptions). In fact, the geriatrician often reviews the medical history and often de-prescribes (especially those medicines that contribute to the patient's cognitive worsening). The elderly woman soon found herself falling asleep at different times of the day and waking up disoriented, not knowing what time it was. Sometimes she thought she had already eaten, so she would not eat or take her medication. As a result, her daughter took her into her home, where she now lives. This new household unit consists of 4 people: two young people, one adult and the elderly lady. Both the daughter and the grandchildren monitor the elderly woman's medication, but as they work or study, they cannot be present for every medication intake. In addition, the geriatrician tends to de-prescribe and recommend lifestyle changes (walking, a certain diet, etc.) that place a greater burden on the family members, while the general practitioner tends to prescribe generously, sometimes contributing to the worsening of the elderly lady's health. This situation of different - even antagonistic - prescribing styles by different doctors is something that exists in the case of nursing homes. This was noted by the main informal carer, who is also a health professional and has worked in both pharmacies and nursing homes. Another issue mentioned in relation to care homes is that there are protocols for medication intake management, when the elderly have difficulties swallowing. This could involve crushing different medications together - which can lead to cross-contamination, especially if staff are not trained or knowledgeable about the medications they are using (again, reference was made to the physical characteristics of the medications, such as bright colours, etc.).

Case3: The third case is a three-generation family who live in an urban Hungarian city, the mother, 88 years old, is cared for by her son, 57 years old, and her granddaughter, 23 years old, she suffers from chronic illnesses such as heart disease, diabetes, and varicose veins at the same time, and she takes seven or eight medications a day, of which three are mandatory, which her family doctor usually prescribes, and which she occasionally visits the hospital for, as the medications are out of the family doctor's scope of treatment. She doesn't have any mental illnesses and her husband was a pharmacist before he died and they ran a pharmacy together for decades until her husband died so she can manage her medications on her own and knows the basic interactions of the medications. Meanwhile, her granddaughter helps her with her weekly medication schedule for each week and checks on her medication intake from time to time but this year her granddaughter is graduating and looking for a job and will not always stay at home to look after her, so she is planning to go to a nursing home this March. She spends a very large amount of time watching TV

every day, and although she has experience in running a pharmacy, she is often influenced by the advertisements on TV and asks for medicines that claim to make her healthier or reduce certain symptoms (e.g., itching, etc.). From time to time, she would also ask for a change of medication on the pretext of itchy skin, joint pain, etc., this made her 57-year-old son very worried, thinking that too much medication would destroy his mother's health and that maybe these medications could relieve some of her pain or discomfort, but the side effects of the medications could also be really serious for an elderly person. And the unpleasant experiences of their neighbours¹⁸ in nursing homes added to his concerns.

Case4: Case 4 is a 27-year-old grandson taking care of his 86-year-old grandfather, and his 88-year-old grandmother helping out as much as she can. They live in a city in northern China, the grandfather suffers from high blood pressure, cerebral thrombosis, inability to speak, hemiplegia on the right side of his body, inability to move, and relatively forgetfulness. The main medications he usually takes are cerebral thrombosis medication, antihypertensive medication, insomnia medication and medication for diuresis and defecation. Most of the medications are controlled medications, so they have to be prescribed regularly at the hospital. For some minor health conditions (e.g., gastrointestinal discomfort) the naturopathic remedies (specific vegetables and fruits) always be used as an assistance of treatment. During the period of taking medication, as the patient is quite forgetful, the medicine he had taken, after a while, he thinks he has not taken it and insist to take it again, even though after being reminded, he still insists that he has not taken it, and sometimes steals it by himself, but since he is taken care of almost 24 hours a day (except for the sleeping time), the situation of an overdose of medication is relatively rare. Occasionally, a month's worth of medication is taken in less than 30 days (more than 20 days), but it is all within the normal timeframe that the hospital can prescribe the medication needed, there have been no instances where the medication could not be picked up. Another situation is that the patient occasionally does not want to take the medication but stores it (pretending to eat it but hiding it in his mouth), but because of the lack of communication (objectively, the patient cannot speak, and subjectively, the patient does not want to talk about it), it is unknown what the patient's exact thoughts are. One of the reassuring things is that since the patient takes a fixed amount of medication all year round, there is no need for special management, and the family knows exactly what medication is to be taken at what time. His grandson felt that a smart pill box based on reminders would not be useful in their situation and could cause an additional financial burden, especially since his grandfather is very opinionated and stubborn so the AI could not sway him to take his medication or not. He felt that the most fundamental approach was to have more companionship and care from family members and that the burden on carers could be reduced if patient data could be collected through AI monitoring technology and then fed back to family members so that they could remotely observe the patient's condition.

¹⁸ Their neighbour was abused by a nurse in the nursing home.

6. Discussion and Conclusion

The study combines the experiences of health experts with four elderly care scenarios. The elderly individuals in these scenarios reside in private homes and household units that correspond to multigenerational families. Regarding medication use, in exploring the medication habits of older people in different contexts, we found some commonalities and nuances. Some respondents were proactive, combining prescribed medication with natural remedies and maintaining open communication with neighbours. However, some respondents faced the challenge of conflicting prescriptions from family doctors and specialists, reflecting the complexity of managing multiple medications. At the same time, these interviews show that family support, community support and neighbourhood support are important in managing medications, especially if the patient is unable to communicate effectively with their caregivers.

When it comes to misuse, the interviews shed light on substance abuse among the elderly. Forgetfulness can lead to repeat medication use, and some older people have deliberately hidden or stolen medication, highlighting the importance of family presence and monitoring, as well as the vulnerability of older people to advertised medicines, which can lead to concerns about over-medication or potential medication interactions. Furthermore, some respondents had to cope with conflicting prescriptions from different healthcare professionals, leading to uncertainty and potential overuse.

In this light, the social and environmental factors surrounding medication misuse in the elderly play a critical role in shaping healthcare outcomes. Intergenerational cohabitation may lead to the accumulation of medications in households, necessitating careful management. However, the study highlights the central role of the family in caring for the elderly, most of them are polymedicated and presenting a variety of health conditions. Informal caregivers play a crucial role in the medication management of older adults. They are present throughout the entire process, from prescription to collection and administration. Although this arrangement is less risky than institutional care, the different generations' and family members' medications can lead to medication accumulation in households. Therefore, careful management is necessary. Each case involves a degree of dependency on informal caregivers. The literature review shows that informal caregivers can be negligent in caring for older people, intentionally or unintentionally, due to burden. Our study echoes this information, especially when several informal caregivers are implicated. This can be aggravated when several health professionals with conflicting ideas and protocols are involved. For this, in the medication management process, healthcare providers can actively engage in conversations with patients or their family members, ensuring a thorough understanding of medication effectiveness, side effects, and dosage. Using a simple medication reconciliation form or giving instructions in a written format, providers can verify prescribed medications and assess potential obstacles for the elderly or their family members in timely medication acquisition. Formulating practical solutions, maintaining proper documentation, and scheduling follow-up appointments/check-ups for regular reassessment of adherence, practising de-prescription when needed, and addressing emerging challenges are integral components of this approach. Employing these methods may contribute to optimising medication management for elderly patients.

The study also addresses the importance of health literacy. Improved health literacy is crucial in preventing the misuse of medication among the elderly. It is important to be aware of the characteristics, uses, and risks of medications. There is a need for widespread awareness of the risks associated with inappropriate use of medicines among the elderly. It is also important to raise awareness about ageist and sexist biases that have become normalised and may be affecting the prescription of medicines. In addition, caution was made visible with the implementation of artificial intelligence-based systems, which may perpetuate - even exacerbate - these biases. Focusing on respondents' attitudes towards AI concerns about potential abuse and neglect in nursing homes or other care facilities were also mentioned in the interviews, and it was felt that AI tools should be used to enhance monitoring or reduce the use of manpower to prevent elder abuse. Some interviewees also hoped that AI technology could be used to provide oversight of seniors' health and medication intake, reducing the risk of forgetfulness, intentional misuse, or conflicting medical opinions, but did not think that the common smart pillboxes, which are currently focused on reminders, would be more effective.

Related to this, digital medication management systems, by reducing reliance on human intervention, have the potential to mitigate instances of medication misuse among the elderly arising from caregivers' proactive actions (motivated by time-saving or abuse). The precision and continuous operation of machines contribute to minimising errors in medication usage by the elderly. However, excessive dependence on digital systems may introduce new risks of medication misuse. This is because these systems essentially make decisions on medication adherence and timing for the elderly, limiting their ability to adjust based on personal responses (such as adverse effects prompting a need for a substitute within the same medicine class). Therefore, a balanced collaboration between human oversight and machine functionality is imperative for optimal outcomes.

Societal stereotypes associating ageing with illness contribute to overprescription and unnecessary medicalization, impacting the health and well-being of the elderly. Cultural differences in medication perception, such as the normalisation of sleeping pills in certain populations, influence patterns of medication use. The limited inclusion of elderly individuals in clinical trials hampers our understanding of medication efficacy and safety in this demographic. In this light, priority should be given to researching this issue, and designing research protocols that successfully capture the situation. Meanwhile, the shortage of skilled medical personnel, especially in rural areas, exacerbates the issue. Vulnerable elderly individuals without social security coverage or insurance lack adequate support, with the underfunded social assistance model falling short of meeting their needs. In rural settings, demand for both healthcare professionals and social workers intensifies, compounding the difficulty in ensuring medication safety for this demographic. Addressing ageism and sexism as well as improving the social protection coverage in healthcare is crucial to ensuring equitable and appropriate healthcare for the elderly.

In conclusion, this research achieved a better understanding of prescribed medication misuse in the elderly (+65) with a special focus on exploring elderly person-centred approaches to medicine prescription, medication safety, especially in polypharmacy and secure access to the required medication (for each patient). This research - articulated around the following research questions: (1) How does the social environment, including formal and informal care providers, influence

(exacerbate or mitigate) prescribed medicine misuse among older adults?; (2) What are the best practices for healthcare providers and caregivers to strike a balance between ensuring medication access and preventing misuse among the elderly?, and (3) which digital or technological systems/solutions might be best suited to support safe use of controlled medicines in older populations? – this research is new, as it has explored an under-researched topic, producing novel knowledge, as there are hardly any studies on the subject. This research has therefore contributed to filling a gap in research and, at the same time, shedding light on a central phenomenon for the UN (see section 1. Introduction). Thus, it has allowed us to gain a better understanding of the issue by highlighting the fact that to safeguard the elderly from medication misuse, a comprehensive, yet personalised, approach is imperative.

First and foremost, prescribing procedures need enhancement through thorough assessments of medical history, considering underlying conditions, potential medication interactions, and overall health status. Individualised prescriptions, tailored to the unique needs of elderly patients, must follow, with careful consideration of factors like liver and kidney function to minimise adverse effects. Educational initiatives aimed at informal caregivers and elderly individuals are crucial, emphasising safe medication use, understanding prescribed doses, and recognizing potential side effects. Artificial intelligence like smart pill boxes is still questionable among experts, but the positive attitude comes to the much more advanced integrating technology, such as smart home systems, which can aid in managing medication schedules, and on the other hand, AI technology should be provided user-friendly for the elderly. It is essential to challenge societal stereotypes associating ageing with illness, fostering a nuanced understanding to reduce unnecessary medicalization. Interdisciplinary collaboration among healthcare professionals, caregivers, and patients is paramount, ensuring holistic medication management, especially during transitions of care. Regular medication reviews and evaluations should be established, addressing cases of polypharmacy or outdated prescriptions, with an emphasis on lifestyle changes that may reduce medication reliance.

All of these findings have allowed us to craft a series of policy recommendations with the aim of providing our agency, UNODC, with some useful advice based on solid evidence (see Appendix C). These policy recommendations ¹⁹are structured in eight broad topics with the intention to facilitate the further categorising of our advice hierarchically (that is, in policies, strategies, programs, and activities), to foster their implementation. This decision was taken aiming maximising the success of our goal: minimising the risk of misuse/misprescription of medications in older adults, which can lead to an impoverishment of the patients' health and to flaws in the drug supply chain (such as medication leaks). These overarching categories are: (1) Legislation Adjustment, (2) Universal Health System Support, (3) Improve Social Awareness and Combating the Stereotype, (4) Prescription Standardisation and Monitoring, (5) Enhancing the Literacy, (6)

¹⁹ In the Legislation Adjustment part of the policy recommendation, we use the “drug control legislation” instead of the “medication control legislation” is because at the international level, the current fundamental legal system based on three international conventions of controlled drugs (the Single Convention on Narcotic Drugs of 1961 (as amended by the 1972 Protocol), the Convention on Psychotropic Substances of 1971, and the United Nations Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances of 1988.) which serve as universal legal benchmarks, and at the national level, there is still a lack of systematic and effective laws and regulations to systematically regulate the source, diversion and monitoring of controlled medicines.

Healthcare Infrastructure Enhancement, (7) Patient-centric support and Transition Improvement, (8) Improve Medical Glossary and Clear Definitions.

7. Bibliography

- Andersson, H., Lindholm, M., Pettersson, M., & Jonasson, L. L. (2017). Nurses' competencies in home healthcare: an interview study. *BMC nursing*, 16, 65. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-017-0264-9> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Bally, E. L., Van Grieken, A., Ye, L., Ferrando, M., Fernández-Salido, M., Dix, R., Zanutto, O., Gallucci, M., Vasiljev, V., Carroll, Á., Darley, A., Gil-Salmerón, A., Ortet, S., Rentoumis, T., Kavoulis, N., Mayora-Ibarra, O., Karanasiou, N., Koutalieris, G., Hazelzet, J. A. Mackiewicz, K. (2022). 'Value-based Methodology for Person-centred, Integrated care supported by Information and Communication Technologies' (ValueCare) for Older people in Europe: study protocol for a pre-post controlled trial. *BMC Geriatrics*, 22(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12877-022-03333-8> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Boddiger D. Medicationabuse in older US adults worries experts[J]. *Lancet*, 2008, 372(9650): 1622. DOI:10.1016/S0140-6736(08)61672-4
- Chau, P. Y., & Hu, P. J. H. (2002). Investigating healthcare professionals' decisions to accept telemedicine technology: an empirical test of competing theories. *Information & Management*, 39(4), 297-311.
- Culberson, J., & Ziska, M. (2008). Prescription medication misuse/abuse in the elderly. *PubMed*, 63(9), 22-31. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18763848> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Culberson, J., & Ziska, M. (2008). Prescription medication misuse/abuse in the elderly. *PubMed*, 63(9), 22-31. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/18763848> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- De Lema Larre, B. (2015). Addiction, Mental Health and dual Pathology in Geriatrics. *Journal of Psychology & Clinical Psychiatry*. <https://doi.org/10.15406/jpcpy.2015.02.00114> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Dowling, G. J., Weiss, S. R., & Condon, T. P. (2007). Medications of abuse and the aging brain. *Neuropsychopharmacology*, 33(2), 209-218. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.npp.1301412> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Dyb, K., Berntsen, G., & Kvam, L. (2021). Adopt, adapt, or abandon technology-supported person-centred care initiatives: healthcare providers' beliefs matter. *BMC Health Services Research*, 21(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-021-06262-1> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Edvardsson D. (2015): Notes on person-centred care: What it is and what it is not. *Nordic Journal of Nursing Research*. 35(2):65-66. doi:10.1177/0107408315582296
- Ekman, I., Britten, N., Bordin, J., Codagnone, C., Edén, S., Forslund, D., Fredman, P., Grip, L., Hedman, H., Hesselbom, T., Hard, I., Larkö, O., Lindström, I., Lindström, L., Norberg, A., Olauson, A., Rosén, H., Seddigh, A., Tennant, A., . . . Swedberg, K. (2013). The person-centred approach to an ageing society. *European Journal for Person Centered Healthcare*, 1(1), 132. <https://doi.org/10.5750/ejpc.v1i1.644> Accessed on 29/11/2023

- Glomsås, Heidi Snoen et al. "User involvement in the implementation of welfare technology in home care services: The experience of health professionals-A qualitative study." *Journal of clinical nursing* vol. 29,21-22 (2020): 4007-4019. doi:10.1111/jocn.15424
- Gossop, M. & Moos, R. (2008) Substance misuse among older adults: a neglected but treatable problem. *Addiction*, 103(3), 347-348. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1360-0443.2007.02096.x> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Han, B., Gfroerer, J., Colliver, J. D., & Penne, M. (2009). Substance use disorder among older adults in the United States in 2020. *Addiction*, 104(1), 88-96. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1360-0443.2008.02411.x> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Harris, M., & Rogers, W. (2023). Developing a Healthcare Technology Acceptance Model (H-TAM) for Older Adults with Hypertension. *Ageing & Society*, 43(4), 814-834. doi:10.1017/S0144686X21001069
- Holtfreter, K., Reisig, M. D., & O'Neal, E. N. (2015). Prescription Medication Misuse in Late Adulthood: An Empirical Examination of Competing Explanations. *Journal of Medication Issues*, 45(4), 351-367. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022042615589405> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Hung, L. (2020). Using virtual care interventions to provide person-centred care to hospitalised older people with dementia. *Nursing Older People*. <https://doi.org/10.7748/nop.2020.e1294> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Immonen, S., Valvanne, J., & Pitkälä, K. H. (2013). The prevalence of potential alcohol-medication interactions in older adults. *Scandinavian Journal of Primary Health Care*, 31(2), 73-78. <https://doi.org/10.3109/02813432.2013.788272> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- International Narcotics Control Board (INCB). The report of the International Narcotics Control Board for 2020 (E/INCB/2020/1). http://www.incb.org/documents/Publications/AnnualReports/AR2020/Annual_Report/E_INCB_2020_1_eng.pdf Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Introduction to Person-centred Care for Older People in Care Homes - SCIE. (s. f.). Social Care Institute for Excellence (SCIE). <https://www.scie.org.uk/person-centred-care/older-people-care-homes/introduction> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Iqbal, Sarfraz; Jokela, Päivi; Hammar, Tora; and Nilsson, Anna-Lena (2021) "Sustainable Healthcare Systems. A holistic perspective on the use and impact of medication management robots in home healthcare," *Scandinavian Journal of Information Systems: Vol. 33: Iss. 2, Article 6*. <https://aisel.aisnet.org/sjis/vol33/iss2/6> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Johansson-Pajala, R. M., & Gustafsson, C. (2022). Significant challenges when introducing care robots in Swedish elder care. *Disability and rehabilitation. Assistive technology*, 17(2), 166–176. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17483107.2020.1773549> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- José Joaquín Mira (2019) Medication errors in the older people population, *Expert Review of Clinical Pharmacology*, 12:6, 491-494, DOI: 10.1080/17512433.2019.1615442

- Kleiven, H.H., Ljunggren, B. & Solbjør, M. Health professionals' experiences with the implementation of a digital medication dispenser in home care services – a qualitative study. *BMC Health Serv Res* 20, 320 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-020-05191-9> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Knaul, F. M., Farmer, P. E., Krakauer, E. L., De Lima, L., Bhadelia, A., Jiang Kwete, X., Arreola-Ornelas, H., Gómez-Dantés, O., Rodriguez, N. M., Alleyne, G. A. O., Connor, S. R., Hunter, D. J., Lohman, D., Radbruch, L., Del Rocío Sáenz Madrigal, M., Atun, R., Foley, K. M., Frenk, J., Jamison, D. T., Rajagopal, M. R., ... Lancet Commission on Palliative Care and Pain Relief Study Group (2018). Alleviating the access abyss in palliative care and pain relief-an imperative of universal health coverage: the Lancet Commission report. *Lancet* (London, England), 391(10128), 1391–1454. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(17\)32513-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(17)32513-8) Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Laatikainen, O., Sneek, S. & Turpeinen, M. Medication-related adverse events in health care—what have we learned? A narrative overview of the current knowledge. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol* 78, 159–170 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00228-021-03213-x> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Lofwall, M. R., Brooner, R. K., Bigelow, G. E., Kindbom, K., & Strain, E. C. (2005). Characteristics of older opioid maintenance patients. *Journal of Substance Abuse Treatment*, 28(3), 265-272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsat.2005.01.007> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Marcus Persson, Andreas Wallo. 2022. Automation and Public Service Values in Human Resource Management. *Service Automation in the Public Sector*, pages 91-108.
- Mun, Y. Y., Jackson, J. D., Park, J. S., & Probst, J. C. (2006). Understanding information technology acceptance by individual professionals: Toward an integrative view. *Information & management*, 43(3), 350-363.
- Nakrem, S., Solbjør, M., Pettersen, I.N. et al. Care relationships at stake? Home healthcare professionals' experiences with digital medicine dispensers – a qualitative study. *BMC Health Serv Res* 18, 26 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-2835-1> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Nchako, E., Bussell, S., Nesbeth, C., & Odoh, C. (2018). Barriers to the availability and accessibility of controlled medicines for chronic pain in Africa. *International health*, 10(2), 71–77. <https://doi.org/10.1093/inthealth/ihy002> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Palinkas LA, Horwitz SM, Green CA, Wisdom JP, Duan N, Hoagwood K. Purposeful Sampling for Qualitative Data Collection and Analysis in Mixed Method Implementation Research. *Adm Policy Ment Health*. 2015 Sep;42(5):533-44. doi: 10.1007/s10488-013-0528-y. PMID: 24193818; PMCID: PMC4012002.
- Paula A Rochon, MD, MPH, FRCPC. "Medicationprescribing for older adults." <https://www.uptodate.com/contents/medication-prescribing-for-older-adults/print> Accessed on 29/11/2023
- Persson, M., Redmalm, D., & Iversen, C. (2021). Caregivers' use of robots and their effect on work environment – a scoping review. *Journal of Technology in Human Services*, 40(3), 251–277. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15228835.2021.2000554> Accessed on 29/11/2023

Qato, D. M., Alexander, G. C., Conti, R. M., Johnson, M., Schumm, L. P., & Lindau, S. T. (2008). Use of prescription and over-the-counter medications and dietary supplements among older adults in the United States. *JAMA*, 300(24), 2867. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2008.892> Accessed on 29/11/2023

Rosen, D., Smith, M. L., & Reynolds, C. F. (2008). The prevalence of mental and physical health disorders among older methadone patients. *American Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*, 16(6), 488-497. <https://doi.org/10.1097/jgp.0b013e31816ff35a> Accessed on 29/11/2023

Schelis, L.; Walter, R. Digital Networking in Home-Based Support of Older Adults in Rural Areas: Requirements for Digital Solutions. *Sustainability* 2021, 13, 1946. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13041946> Accessed on 29/11/2023

Schweitzer, M., & Hoerbst, A. (2016). Robotic Assistance in Medication Management: Development and Evaluation of a Prototype. *Studies in health technology and informatics*, 225, 422–426.

Thompson AAB, Sachdev K, Das-Munshi J, et al. Substance misuse in older adults with frailty[J]. *BMJ*, 2019(364): 1958. DOI:10.1136/bmj.1958

UNODC 2010: Resolution 53/4 - Promoting adequate availability of internationally controlled licit medications for medical and scientific purposes while preventing their diversion and abuse

UNODC 2011a: Ensuring availability of controlled medications for the relief of pain and preventing diversion and abuse.

UNODC 2011a: Ensuring availability of controlled medications for the relief of pain and preventing diversion and abuse.

UNODC 2011b: The non-medical use of prescription medications.

UNODC 2018: Increasing access and availability of controlled medicines

Webster F, Rice K. Conducting ethnography in primary care. *Fam Pract*. 2019 Jul 31;36(4):523–5. doi: 10.1093/fampra/cmz007. PMID: PMC6669036.

李冰. 老年人的物质依赖[J]. *实用老年医学*, 2003(2): 68-71. Li B. Substance dependence of the elderly[J]. *Practical Geriatrics*, 2003(2): 68-71.

熊风, 赖玉清, 涂嘉欣, 等. 中国老年人群睡眠障碍流行特征的Meta分析[J]. *中国循证医学杂志*, 2019, 19(4): 398-403. Xiong F, Lai YQ, Tu JX, et al. Epidemiological characteristics of sleep disorders in the Chinese elderly: a Meta-analysis[J]. *Chin J Evid Based Med*, 2019, 19(4): 398-403.

肖立群. 老年苯二氮卓类药物依赖患者生活质量对照研究[J]. *社区医学杂志*, 2012, 10(9): 3-5. Xiao LQ. A controlled study of the quality of life in senile patients with benzodiazepine dependence[J]. *J Commun Med*, 2012, 10(9): 3-5.

贡坤瑶, 徐军, 杨泽. 老年人抑郁症患病特征和相关因素的分析研究[J]. *中国老年保健医学*, 2018, 16(5): 90-92. Gong KY, Xu J, Yang Z. Analysis of related factors of depression in the elderly population[J]. *Chin J Geriatr Care*, 2018, 16(5): 90-92.

8. Appendix

8.1. Appendix A - Figures used for this study

Life expectancy of people aged 65 years, by sex, 2010-2015

Note: the figure is ranked on average (both sexes) life expectancy at 65 years. The information details average life expectancy for the period from 2010 to 2015.

Source: Eurostat (online data code: demo_mlexpec) and United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, World Population Prospects 2019

eurostat

Figure 1: Life expectancy of people aged 65 years, by sex, 2010-2015 (years). Source: EUROSTAT - Ageing Europe - statistics on health and disability.²⁰

²⁰https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Ageing_Europe_-_statistics_on_health_and_disability#Life_expectancy_and_healthy_life_years_among_older_people

Figure 2: Prescribed medicines taken by an elderly person in a bad state of health, after fainting.²¹

Figure 3: Self-reported use of prescribed medicines by sex, age and country of citizenship. Unit of measure: Percentage. Source of data: Eurostat.

²¹ This person and family were not selected to continue the interviews with due to the elderly person's poor state of health.

Total use of prescribed medicines by age group

Data source: INE - European Health Survey 2020. Self reported use of prescribed medicines over 2 weeks. Units: years and percentages

Figure 4: Percentage of the total amount of prescribed medicines by age-group in Spain. Source of the Data: INE – European Health Survey 2020.

Use of prescribed medicines in older adults (+65) by age group and gender

Data source: INE - European Health Survey 2020. Self reported use of prescribed medicines over 2 weeks. Units: years and percentages

Figure 5: Percentage of the total amount of prescribed medicines by age-group within +56 years old in Spain. Source of the Data: INE – European Health Survey 2020.

Use of prescribed medicines in older adults (+65) by type of medicine

Data source: INE - European Health Survey 2020. Self reported use of prescribed medicines over 2 weeks. Units: percentages

Figure 5: Percentage of medicines prescribed to elderly people by type of medicine in Spain.
Source of the Data: INE – European Health Survey 2020.

Use of prescribed medicines in older adults (+65) by type of medicine and gender

Data source: INE - European Health Survey 2020. Self reported use of prescribed medicines over 2 weeks. Units: percentages

Figure 6: Percentage of medicines prescribed to elderly people by type of medicine and gender in Spain. Source of the Data: INE – European Health Survey 2020.

8.2. Appendix B - Questionnaire for experts [template to adjust to each case]

QUESTIONNAIRE DESCRIPTION

Description of our research:

This research aims to analyse **prescribed medication misuse in the elderly (+65)** with a special focus on exploring (1) elderly person-centred approaches to medicine prescription, (2) medication safety, especially in polypharmacy and (3) secure access to the required medication (for each patient). With Spain as a study case, we aim at exploring

- (1) How does the **social environment**, including formal and informal care providers, influence (exacerbate or mitigate) prescribed medicine misuse among older adults?
- (2) What are the **best practices for healthcare providers and caregivers** to strike a balance between ensuring medication access and preventing misuse among the elderly?
- (3) which **digital or technological systems/solutions** might be best suited to support safe use of controlled medicines in older populations?

Goals and outcome of the interview:

- Write a report with the findings, combining results from this experts' interview with the rest of our research results.
- This report will be submitted to be reviewed by RAUN team. The report will be also shared with the mentor from UNODC.
- In its final version, it will be shared at UN headquarters in Viena in the form of a presentation and published as a public available document at RAUN webpage.

Goals and outcome of the research:

- Write advice document on policy making for UNODC, regarding the implementation of measurements for addressing the misused of controlled medicines in older adults.

Conditions of the interview:

- Participation is voluntary. The participant is free to stop collaborating the moment they decide.
- Questions will be given in advance to the experts.
- Experts can add or exclude anything they want at any point of the interview.
- The conversation will be transcribed for analysing purposes.
- The text will be shared with the experts before publication for reviewing if they want to.

Number of questions: 7

Type of questions: Open

QUESTIONS

General questions:

According to your experience, is misuse among older adults in Spain an important issue? Have you come across any cases or very severe cases of misuse of prescribed medicines in older populations? (feel free to share your experience globally, list different cases, provide an in-depth case that is/was specially telling of the overall situation).

According to your experience, do you think there is enough social awareness around this issue? (Is the misuse identified as such when it happens? Are people aware that misuse is a threat to older adult's wellbeing?).

Which are the social and cultural characteristics that conditions the use of prescribed medicines in Spain (role of the caregivers, medical facilities, family implication etc. rural environments vs. city environments etc.) This can be done focusing on the Spanish case in general, comparing different regions (Comunidades Autónomas), or addressing other areas or trends within the European region for a contrast.

Focusing on AP, which would be the role of AP teams in this issue? (Feel free to share any thoughts on the specific ways in which the role of AP professionals is fundamental to this question, both at the stage of detecting the misuse, preventing potential future misuse or trying to redirect certain situations).

Focus questions:

Our research so far suggests that the elderly confront a dual paradox. On one side, stringent regulation in a response to substance abuse crises may hinder their access to certain medications. Conversely, the elderly may be susceptible to substance misuse because of the number of prescribed medications, potential interactions between medications, and instances of overprescription aimed at simplifying caregiving for older individuals. In your experience, is this the case? Have you any thoughts on how we could prevent this from happening?

During our research, we have observed the use of different digital and technological solutions when it comes to prescribed medication intake management (alarms, calendars, technological medical devices...). According to your experience, are those really beneficial? What should be taken into account when considering the implementation of digital or technological solutions to help assuring safety medication?

Our research has also made us reflect on the category "older population" as +65, given the variety of health situations that exist and the strong differences between people aged close to 65 or more than 80. Similarly, our research suggests that women are prescribed more medications than men, especially when it comes to antidepressants, tranquilisers and pain killers, and are therefore more at risk of misuse. Do you have any thoughts on how to manage such a diverse population, and the reasons for such differences?

Final questions:

Please, feel free to add whatever you want: is there anything that you consider important and we haven't covered yet? Is there anything else that you wanted to add?

8.3. Appendix C - Policy recommendations

Policy Recommendations	
Legislation Adjustment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review drug control laws to remove barriers for older adults' access to prescribed medications. • Propose legislative amendments addressing economic, regulatory, and healthcare provider challenges. • Advocate for enhanced regulations, increased budget, and manpower to secure medicine access for vulnerable elderly, including free medical care or social assistance. • Establish and enforce pharmacy operation standards for safety. • Develop policies for older adult inclusion in drug trials to test efficacy and safety.
Universal Health System Support Implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a policy framework for a universal health system, ensuring older adults' access to public healthcare amid economic pressures. • Develop policies promoting collaboration across agencies, departments, and professionals in elderly care. • Advocate for collaboration between relevant agencies like UNODC and WHO to address healthcare crises impacting older populations.
Tackling socio-cultural factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roll out supportive policies for targeted outreach campaigns on elderly misuse of prescribed medications, to raise awareness across society. • Implement policies prioritizing individual health needs irrespective of age, promoting neutral treatment approaches in healthcare to deter unnecessary medicalization and age-related biases. • Integrate an intersectional approach into mental health policies, particularly addressing ageism and sexism in diagnosing and treating mental health issues among elderly women.
Prescription Standardization and Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enforce uniform medication templates and tracking protocols to ensure consistent prescribing practices. • Roll out educational initiatives promoting adherence to WHO food pyramid guidelines among the elderly, providing accessible resources to enhance awareness of healthy eating habits. • Introduce a comprehensive "medication pyramid" model to improve health literacy on medication usage, categorizing medications by purpose and potential effects. • Set up robust monitoring systems to facilitate collaboration among healthcare professionals, pharmacies, and digital solutions for effective tracking and management of prescribed medication intake.
Literacy Enhancement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allocate resources to develop and implement a cognitive impairment policy, promoting social engagement and healthy aging while reducing cognitive decline burden. • Introduce health education policies targeting youth for early intervention in aging-related health concerns, empowering future generations. • Enhance healthcare policy by prioritizing drug literacy promotion and educating individuals about different drugs for informed decision-making. • Promote medical education advancement by integrating narrative medicine principles into curricula and supporting provider communication training.
Healthcare Infrastructure Enhancement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement a supportive policy for developing primary care teams emphasizing holistic approaches to personal and family histories. • Develop digital healthcare policies integrating solutions like electronic medical records and telemedicine platforms to enhance efficiency and accessibility while addressing system costs and data security.
Patient-centric Support and Transition Improvement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement guidelines mandating adequate time for medication counselling during healthcare visits, supported by training programs and incentivized reimbursement structures. • Launch community outreach policies to bolster community-based support for the elderly, facilitating regular medication reviews by healthcare professionals, promoting intergenerational cohabitation, and discouraging medication accumulation at home. • Develop standardized transition protocols, including comprehensive medication reconciliation processes, interoperable information systems, and mandatory communication channels between healthcare providers.
Improve intelligibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer clear definitions for terms (i.e. "older adults," "misuse," "misprescription," "deprescribing," etc.) to ensure common, effective communication.